

Investigation on homothetic failure envelopes in the layer-based fatigue analysis of cfrp

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LAYER-BASED FATIGUE ANALYSIS

- The layer-based fatigue analysis takes place on the lamina level (meso-scale) within a representative volume element (RVE).
- The general approach is based on iterative ply-wise calculations of the in-plane stresses of each layer in a laminate and the subsequent analysis of the material condition (see Figure 1).
- For a multiaxial approach, the in-plane shear and transverse tension strength are coupled via a so called ξ -Model.
- Within the ξ -Model, the SN-curves for any biaxiality ratio ($\xi = \tan^{-1}(\tau_{21} / \sigma_2)$) are calculated with the use of the static failure criteria by Puck [1] (see Figure 2) and the nonlinear residual strength model by Stojkovic et al. [2].

Figure 1: Lifetime Estimation of Composites flowchart [3].

HOMOTHETIC FAILURE ENVELOPES

- A homothetic downsizing of the failure envelope means, that the static inclines are held constant within the fatigue analysis:

$$p_{\perp\parallel}^+ = const., \quad p_{\perp\parallel}^- = const., \quad p_{\perp\perp}(n) = \frac{p_{\perp\perp}}{S_{\perp\perp}(n)} \cdot R_{\perp\perp}^A \neq const.$$

Figure 2: Modeling the failure envelope with residual strength data after a pure in-plane shear load.

MATERIAL TESTS AND INPUT DATA

- The material tests are performed with the servo-hydraulic Tension-Torsion test machine INSTRON 8802 (100 kN/ 1000 Nm) for combined biaxial loads on tube specimen.

- Only data of uni-directional [±90] tubes (radial-wound) is used as simulation input data.
- The input data, which is used for the simulation of the multiaxial loaded laminates, is shown in Figure 3.

Stiffness properties	SN-curve parameter	Strength parameter
E_{\parallel}	133.40 GPa	C_0 8.96E+26
E_{\perp}	8.19 GPa	k_0 16.2
$G_{\perp\parallel}$	4.08 GPa	C_{90} 6.67E+40
$V_{\perp\parallel}$	0.275	k_{90} 21.6
Y_f	43.38 MPa	α_{90} 0.320
$S_{\perp\parallel}$	69.96 MPa	β_{90} 0.170

Figure 3: Input data from experimental tests on uni-directional tube specimen.

RESULTS

- In Figure 4, the predictions for the uniaxial and multiaxial loaded ($\xi = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ, 90^\circ$) UD [±90] (radial-wound) tube-specimen are compared to experimental data.
- In Figure 5, the predictions for the multiaxial loaded ($\xi = 48.8^\circ$) balanced angle-ply with a stacking sequence of [±70] is compared to experimental data.

Figure 4: Verification for uniaxial loaded UD (Left) and Validation for multiaxial loaded UD (Right).

Figure 5: Validation for a multiaxial loaded balanced angle-ply with the stacking sequence [±70].

REFERENCES

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